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Strategies for co-expression of Bilin-producing Enzymes in
Escherichia coli

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Protein cofactors vastly expand the chemical space of proteins and thus allow for otherwise inaccessible functionalities. For instance, heme for oxygen transport, flavins that are key to redox reactions, or copper ions facilitating electron transport, are only some examples amongst a plethora of other protein cofactors. In the protein family of phytochromes, bilin compounds act as cofactors and govern their core functionality – the sensing of red/far-red light. This light-sensing capability regulates central metabolic pathways in plants but also other light-regulated organisms, thus, understanding their molecular mechanisms is of great interest. For biochemical characterization, the phytochrome proteins are most commonly overexpressed in heterologous expression hosts. However, many hosts, like *Escherichia coli*, lack the machinery to produce sufficient levels of bilins. For the generation of biliverdin, this can be alleviated by the co-expression of a heme oxygenase and the phytochrome, most commonly in a two plasmid (helper plasmid/expression plasmid) setup. In this chapter, we introduce two alternative strategies, bi-cistronic co-expression and genomic integration of the heme oxygenase. The generation of these systems is shown in detail and their advantages/disadvantages are discussed compared to the well-established two plasmid systems. We anticipate that these approaches are also feasible for other bilins, for example phytochromobilin and/or phycocyanobilin, which will expand the toolbox for phytochrome expression and provide alternatives for challenging study designs.

Key words

photoreceptor, pigment, heme oxygenase, biliverdin, CRISPR, Cas9, pEcCas, pEcgRNA, genomic integration, bi-cistronic, co-translational,

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Co-expression of bilin producing enzymes

1 Introduction

Photoreceptor proteins depend on specific pigments to respond to different ambient light conditions ranging from the ultra-violet region to the near infra-red part of the electromagnetic spectrum. The employed cofactors (in the visible region) or the amino acid tryptophan itself (UV absorption) enable proteins to integrate information of surrounding light conditions and eventually regulate downstream signal integration partners for organismal adaptation **(1)**. In the family of phytochrome photoreceptors, different linear tetrapyrroles (bilins) derived from heme are used as the light sensing cofactors and the degree of bilin reduction is employed to additionally tune the absorption properties in different organisms **(2)**. With an absorption maximum in the near-IR, biliverdin (BV)-binding phytochromes found in bacteria and fungi have the longest wavelength absorption maxima and only require the action of a heme oxygenase to generate their cofactor from heme **(3)**. Conversely, in plants and cyanobacteria, an additional biliverdin reduction machinery is necessary to produce their preferred phytochrome cofactors phytochromobilin (PΦB) and phycocyanobilin (PCB), respectively **(2)**.

In order to characterize the diverse phytochrome family, heterologous expression is typically required to obtain the amounts needed for a detailed biochemical and biophysical characterization. To this end, apo-phytochromes can be expressed in established bacterial or eukaryotic expression systems and subsequently reconstituted with their corresponding cofactors. However, for some phytochromes instability of the apo form has been reported **(4)** and also concerns about differences between co-translational insertion of the bilin vs. subsequent reconstitution have been raised **(5)**. Therefore, co-expression of bilin producing enzymes together with the phytochrome genes is typically the preferred way of generating holo-protein preparations for biochemical purification and characterization **(6–9)**.

Historically, versatile two plasmid expression systems **(10)** are the most utilized approach with a helper plasmid encoding a heme oxygenase (HO) plus if needed other bilin producing enzymes and a second plasmid containing a phytochrome sequence. An example of this setup is the pT7 helper plasmid containing the *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 *ho1*, first established by Tarutina et al. **(11)**, and modified by

Gourinchas et al., **(4)** in combination with an pETM11 overexpression vector encoding a bacteriophytochrome (BphP).

In this chapter we want to portrait two alternative approaches and how they were generated in our lab. Firstly, usage of a bi-cistronic approach was already reported in previous work **(12)**, however not in an overexpression format as outlined in this chapter. This approach is inspired by natural BphP operon structures, where the phytochrome is often co-encoded with their respective HO gene. This genomic architecture is either achieved with overlapping open-reading frames (ORF, Figure 1D), in line with model overlapping gene sequences like *menD/menH* in *E. coli* **(13)** or with short nucleotide spacers between the HO and BphP gene (Figure 1E). Thus, the awareness for this method should be furthered and possible strategies for the design of such an expression system are discussed in this chapter. Secondly, we introduce an *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) based expression host where the *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 *ho1* gene under the T7 promoter from the pT7 vector was stably integrated into the chromosomal *recA* locus by a CRISPR/Cas9 method modified from Li et al. **(14)**.

Finally, we also want to highlight potential caveats employing the two different systems and compare them to the established helper plasmid/overexpression plasmid systems. Thereby, we provide novel tools for specific use cases, a helpful introduction for those new to the field, but also provide new insights to those who sometimes struggle with the reproducibility of bilin-production in bacterial systems. Though not tested specifically, these approaches should also be amendable for the production of PCB, and PΦB-binding proteins.

Fig. 1. Different approaches for cofactor generation during BphP expression. In all panels, green symbolizes the open reading frame (ORF) of the heme oxygenase and blue the ORF of the phytochrome. A) In the classical established systems, the *ho1* gene, for example from *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803, is provided on a helper plasmid in parallel to an expression plasmid containing the phytochrome of interest. B) Alternatively, the *ho1* gene can be stably integrated into the genome of an expression strain, thus, only the plasmid containing the phytochrome needs to be transformed into the strain. C) Also, the *ho1* and phytochrome can be expressed from a single plasmid with a bicistronic architecture, either with overlapping open reading frames or separated by a short nucleotide spacer. D) Natural genomic context of *MsHO* (green arrow) and *MsPadC* (blue arrow) in *Marinobacter* sp. T13-3. The gene sequence of the HO gene and the adjacent *MsPadC* show overlapping stop (“tga”) and start (“gtg”) codons, respectively. E) Natural genomic context of *IsHO* (green arrow) and *IsPadC* (blue arrow) in *Idiomarina* sp. A28L. The two ORFs are separated by an in-frame nucleotide spacer (white bar) with a length of 87bp.

2 Materials

Prepare all solutions using ultrapure water and chemicals of ACS grade or higher. For the equipment and all kits which are used in this chapter also alternative suppliers can be used, as long as the specified requirements are met. Vector files and gene sequences, which are used in this chapter, are deposited at <https://doi.org/10.3217/tv97k-t9f33> (see **Note 1**).

2.1 General materials

1. Low salt LB medium: 10 g/L tryptone, 5 g/L yeast extract, 5 g/L NaCl
2. LB-Agar plates: autoclave the medium after addition of 18 g/L agar and add the appropriate amounts of antibiotics after cooling to 60 °C and before pouring the plates.

Antibiotic additives (prepare as 1000x stocks) to LB media/plates:

3. LBK media/plates: Kanamycin final conc. 34 µg/mL
4. LBSt media/plates: Streptomycin final conc. 100 µg/mL
5. LBKSt media/plates: Kanamycin final conc. 34 µg/mL, Streptomycin final conc. 100 µg/mL
6. LBCK media/plates: Chloramphenicol final conc. 30 µg/mL, Kanamycin final conc. 34 µg/mL

2.2 Bi-cistronic expression of heme-oxygenase and phytochrome

1. PCR polymerase: use a proofreading polymerase of your choice, for example Q5[®] High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase
2. Coding sequence of the gene of interest: order from your gene synthesis vendor of choice, for example order as GeneArt Strings
3. overexpression target vector: here pETM11 *MsPadC* PSM or pETM11 *IsPadC* PSM
4. PCR cycler: for example, PEQLAB peqSTAR 2x gradient
5. Plasmid isolation kit: for example, VWR peqGold Plasmid MiniPrep Kit I

6. Restriction enzyme to remove methylated plasmid DNA: for example *DpnI*

2.3 CRISPR/Cas9 mediated genomic insertion of *ho1* from *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 into BL21 (DE3)

2.3.1 Generation of plasmid constructs for the CRISPR/Cas9 approach

1. LBSt media: prepare 50 mL
2. LBSt plates
3. pEcCas (Addgene #73227)
4. pEcgRNA (Addgene #166581)
5. N20 sequence design webservice: for example, ATUM (see **Note 2**), this sequence determines the target to which the Cas9 nuclease is guided
6. PCR polymerase: use a proofreading polymerase of your choice, for example Q5[®] High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase
7. cloning strain with F' episome: for example, XL10-Gold (see **Note 3**)
8. bacterial chromosomal DNA isolation kit: for example, GeneJET[™] Genomic DNA purification kit
9. DNA cleanup kit: for example, Zymoclean[™] Gel DNA Recovery Kit
10. Gibson assembly kit: for example, NEBuilder[®] HiFi DNA assembly
11. Plasmid isolation kit: for example, VWR peqGold Plasmid MiniPrep Kit I
12. Primers: (see table 1)

Table 1: Primers to assemble the pEcgRNA N20_{recA} vector and the editing fragment

Primer name	Sequence (5' – 3')
N20_ecgRNA_fwd	ACTGGAAATCTGTGACGCCCGTTTTAGAGCTAGAAATAGCAAGTTAAAATAAGGCTAGTCCGTTATC
N20_ecgRNA_rev	GGGCGTCACAGATTTCCAGTCTGAAACCGCTGCGGCG
uphom_recA_fwd	TAGAGTCGACCTGCAGAAGCGCTATCATCTACAGAGAAATCCGGCG
uphom_recA_rev	CGTGGTGGGTAGCGAAACCC
downhom_recA_fwd	CGTGTTCCAGCATCGATAAACGCACAG
downhom_recA_rev	CTTATGGAGCTGCACATGAAGCGTTGGCGGCAGCAC
HO1_pt7_fwd	TTTCGCTACCCACCACGATCCCGCGAAATTAATACGACTCACTATAG
HO1_pt7_rev	GTTTATCGATGCTGAACACGCGGCGGATTTGTCCTACTCA

2.3.2 Genomic insertion of *ho1* into the *recA* locus of BL21 (DE3)

1. LBK media: prepare 200 mL
2. LBK plates
3. LBKSt plates
4. *E. coli* expression strain: for example, BL21 (DE3)
5. Electroporation device: for example, MicroPulser Electroporator
6. Cuvettes for electroporation: for example, Invitrogen™ Electroporation Cuvettes 0.2 cm (cooled on ice)
7. ddH₂O: filtered, autoclaved, ice cold
8. 50 mL sterile tubes
9. Centrifuge for 50ml tubes: for example, Heraeus Multifuge 3S-R
10. Centrifuge for 1.5ml reaction tubes: for example, Eppendorf 5415R centrifuge
11. 10 % Glycerol in ddH₂O (w/v): autoclaved, ice cold
12. Liquid nitrogen
13. 1 M L-arabinose stock (w/v)
14. Vector pEcgRNA N20_{recA}

2.3.3 Validation of successful genomic integration and curing of pEcCas/pEcgRNA from E. coli BL21 (DE3)

1. LB plates
2. LBSu plates: Sucrose final conc. 20 mg/mL
3. LBSt plates
4. LBK media: prepare 200 mL
5. ddH₂O: sterile, room temperature
6. Inoculation loop
7. UV crosslinker: for example, Stratagene® UV Stratalinker® 1800
8. A plate lid cut in half covered with aluminium foil/duct tape
9. 1 M rhamnose stock (w/v)
10. Printed paper raster: this is used to subdivide plates for the patching experiment. See also **(14)**
11. PCR polymerase: use a cheap polymerase suitable for colony PCR which still has proof-reading capabilities, for example NEB OneTaq® Quick-Load 2x Master Mix.
12. DNA cleanup kit: for example, Zymoclean™ Gel DNA Recovery Kit
13. Primers: see table 2
14. 50 % glycerol (w/v): autoclaved

Table 2: Primers to confirm correct genomic integration of *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 *ho1* sequence

Primer name	sequence
seq_genomic_fwd	CTTCGTTAGTTTCTGCTACGCCTTC
seq_genomic_rev	TTCGGAGGTGGCGAG
seq_genomic_pncC_fwd	ATGAGTGTCAACTTAGCTTCCCAG
seq_genomic_pncC_rev	TGCGTATGCATTGCAGACCTTG

2.3.4 General phytochrome expression protocol

1. Expression strain (see Table 3)
2. Expression vectors (see Table 3)
3. LBK medium/plates OR LBCK medium/plates depending on expression system
4. 30 % w/v Glucose stock: autoclave separate to media and store at RT
5. 1 M MgCl₂ stock: add to LB media before autoclaving
6. 10 mg/mL δ -aminolevulinic acid stock (δ -ALA): store at -20 °C
7. 0.5 M Isopropyl- β -D-thiogalactopyranosid stock (IPTG): store at -20 °C
8. 1 L flask: for example, 1 L Nalgene baffled shake flask
9. 2.5 L flask: for example, 2.5 L Ultra Yield® Flasks
10. Orbital Shaker: 25 mm orbital shaker achieving 130 rpm, for example Infors HT Multitron
Standard
11. Centrifuge: for example, Beckmann Coulter Avanti® J-26XP
12. Rotor: for example, Beckmann Coulter JLA-8.1000

3 Methods

In the last years, multiple different expression systems for BphPs with simultaneous generation of the biliverdin cofactor were employed. As described, the helper plasmid-based system is the most widespread one in the literature, like the above-mentioned pT7 HO1 system. In this chapter, first the generation of the alternative holophytochrome expression systems (versions 2-4, Table 3) is outlined, followed by a general expression protocol and a discussion outlining possible hurdles when using the pT7 HO1 helper plasmid system (see **Note 4**) and a comparison of the benefits of the four approaches shown in Table 3 (see **Note 5**).

Table 3: Overview of phytochrome expression systems used in our lab.

Expression systems	Component 1	Component 2	Component 3
Version 1	BL21 (DE3)	pT7 HO1 Cm ^R helper plasmid	pET vector with BphP
Version 2	BL21 (DE3)	pET vector with overlapping ORF of <i>ho1</i> and <i>bphp</i>	-
Version 3	BL21 (DE3)	pET vector with ORF of <i>ho</i> and <i>bphp</i> gene separated by nucleotide spacer	
Version 4	BL21 (DE3) pEc HO1 (stable chromosomal <i>ho1</i> integration)	-	pET vector with BphP

3.1 Bi-cistronic expression of heme-oxygenase and phytochrome

3.1.1 Identification of a heme-oxygenases for bi-cistronic expression

For many BphPs, the heme oxygenase (HO) and the phytochrome can be found in the same operon. Interestingly, in some phytochromes, the preceding heme-oxygenase shares a sequence overlap of its stop codon with the start codon of the subsequent phytochrome gene, though with a relative frame shift (Figure 1D). In other phytochromes, the heme oxygenase precedes the phytochrome but there is an in-frame nucleotide spacer separating the ORFs of both sequences. Both of these genetic

architectures, overlapping ORFs or sequential ORFs, can be used for overexpressing a heme-oxygenase in tandem with a phytochrome from one single plasmid. For both architectures, sequences were identified that work with our model proteins. A short discussion on their efficiency is provided below (see **Note 5**). In the following, a quick method to identify and confirm these heme oxygenase genes in their natural genomic context using blastp and Alphafold2/Foldseek is shown with examples.

1. Paste the protein sequence of your phytochrome of interest into the blastp webserver (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi?PAGE=Proteins>) to identify the organism of origin. In the test example *MsPadC*, *Marinobacter* sp. T13-3 is identified. Follow the Sequence ID link (KXS53631.1) and then the DBSOURCE accession number (LSRT01000111.1) to access the whole genome shot gun sequencing information. For the test example *IsPadC*, the organism *Idiomarina* sp. A28L is identified. Follow the Sequence ID link (WP_007419415.1), then click on the “Nucleotide” link under “Related information” to access the whole genome shotgun sequence (NZ_AFPO01000007.1).
2. In the list of automatically annotated proteins, look for the accession number of your phytochrome of interest and check the locus of the coding DNA sequence (CDS). Check if there is any hypothetical protein with an overlap of the coding sequence to the phytochrome (as for the *MsPadC* gene) or with a protein in very close proximity (as for the *IsPadC* gene). In the *MsPadC* context, a CDS of a hypothetical protein (KXS53630.1) is identified, harboring a 4 nucleotide overlap with a relative -1 frameshift. For *IsPadC*, a CDS already annotated as “biliverdin-producing heme oxygenase” (WP_007419414.1) is identified with a nucleotide sequence spacer between them.
3. Optional: Put the translated sequence into Alphafold2 (**15**) and check the quality of predictions. If a sufficiently confident structural model can be generated, run Foldseek (**16**) and check if structural similarity to published heme-oxygenases can be observed.

3.1.2 Cloning of for the bi-cistronic expression vector

This section details the cloning of the identified *ho* genes into existing expression vectors of phytochromes. As examples, we use the sequences introduced in section 3.1.1, *MsPadC* (**17**) and *IsPadC* (**4**). For the HO sequence retrieved from *Marinobacter*, the nucleotide sequence was partly codon optimized (see **Note 6**) In our case, the sequence was generated with overlaps to an existing expression plasmid containing a BphP (pETM11 *MsPadC*). There, the *ho* gene was cloned in front/overlapping with the start codon of the His₆ tag and TEV cleavage site (see **Note 7**). For the *Idiomarina* derived sequences, the full *ho* sequence was codon optimized and the nucleotide spacer was left unchanged. The *ho* gene plus spacer was cloned into an expression vector (pETM11 *IsPadC*) in front of the His₆ tag and the TEV cleavage site (see **Note 7**). A general protocol for phytochrome expression using these vectors is shown in section 3.3.

1. Perform overlap extension PCR using 3ng of the expression vector (here a pETM11 vector which already contains a bacteriophytochrome) as template and the synthesized *ho* gene (plus spacer in the case of the *Idiomarina* sequence) plus overlaps to the template in 250 molar excess as mega-primer. Conduct PCR with an annealing temperature of 55°C, an extension time sufficient to amplify the whole template plasmid and 20 cycles (see **Note 8**). Remove the template by *DpnI* digest and transform into the cloning strain followed by plasmid isolation.
2. Identify correct plasmids using Sanger sequencing.

3.2 CRISPR/Cas9 mediated genomic insertion of *ho1* from *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 into BL21 (DE3)

3.2.1 Generation of plasmid constructs for the CRISPR/Cas9 approach

To generate an expression strain with chromosomal integration of a biliverdin producing heme oxygenase, insert the *ho1* gene from *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 under the control of a T7 promoter into a chromosomal locus of choice, here the *recA* locus, (see **Note 9**) of *E. coli* BL21 (DE3). For this purpose, the pEcCas (Addgene #73227)/pEcgRNA (Addgene #166581) system was used (see **Note 9** and **Note 3**) and modified. There are multiple important sequences which need to be generated. First, design the N20 nucleotide spacer which is complementary to the chromosomal target sequence. Clone this sequence in front of the scaffold sequence in the pEcgRNA vector. The N20 nucleotide spacer and the scaffold together form the single guide-RNA (sg-RNA) which binds to the Cas9 nuclease and guides it to the chromosomal locus of choice to induce double strand breakage. Also, a so-called editing fragment has to be designed which contains homologous sequences, for example to the *recA* locus. In between the homologous sequences, the editing fragment contains the CDS for the protein of interest which is to be inserted into the genome, here the *ho1* gene (see Figure 2). Using this technique, a stable insertion of *ho1* into *recA* (*recA::ho1*) is achieved which knocks out the function of the recombinase gene. This insertion makes the strain sensitive to UV radiation which aids in the downstream screening for clones with successful genomic integration of *ho1*. Finally, this protocol results in a strain which generates BV upon IPTG induction which is amenable for phytochrome expression.

1. Design the N20 sequence using the online tool ATUM (see **Note 1**), which suggests the sequence “ACTGGAAATCTGTGACGCCC” for the chosen *recA* locus.
2. Use overlapping primers (see **Note 10**) to insert the N20 nucleotide spacer sequence into the plasmid pEcgRNA before the sg- RNA scaffold sequence (primers: N20_ecgRNA_fwd/rev) to generate the vector pEcgRNA N20_{recA}. The primers amplify the whole plasmid plus the N20

insertion. Transform the PCR mix into chemically competent XL10-Gold cells which circularize the plasmid using the introduced overhangs. Isolate the plasmid and confirm the insertion of the N20_{recA} sequence by Sanger sequencing.

3. Run “killing efficiency” experiments (see **Note 11**) with the sg-RNAs created from the N20 nucleotide spacer and the scaffold sequence in the pEcgRNA N20_{recA} vector.
4. The editing fragment consists of three smaller fragments, the “upstream homology sequence”, the *ho1* gene and the “downstream homology sequence” which were together sub-cloned in this order into the vector pEcgRNA 34 nucleotides after the sg-RNA scaffold sequence. To generate the homology sequences (see **Note 12**), purify genomic DNA from *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) using the bacterial chromosomal DNA isolation kit. Conduct a standard PCR to amplify the 320bp upstream homology sequence (primers: uphom_recA_fwd/rev) from the genomic DNA in parallel to the 270bp downstream homology sequence (primers: downhome_recA_fwd/rev). PCR-amplify the *ho1* gene including the T7 promoter and the rrnB T1 terminator from the plasmid pT7 HO1 Cm^R (primers: HO1_pT7_fwd/rev). Also amplify the pEcgRNA N20_{recA} vector backbone with according primers. Subject all liquid PCR samples to a DNA cleanup-step.
5. Circularize the pEcgRNA N20_{recA} vector backbone, the upstream homology sequence, the *ho1* fragment, and the downstream homology sequence with a Gibson assembly kit.
6. Optional: amplify the editing fragment from the final vector pEcgRNA N20_{recA} +editing Fragment by PCR (primers: uphom_recA_fwd/downhom_recA_rev) followed by a DNA cleanup step using a kit to generate a highly concentrated linear editing fragment stock (~500ng/μL) (see **Note 13**)

3.2.2 Genomic insertion of *ho1* into the *recA* locus of BL21 (DE3)

With the following protocol, the *ho1* sequence is inserted into the *recA* locus, thereby disrupting its open reading frame (Figure 2, see **Note 14**). This is achieved by transforming the plasmid pEcCas (see **Note 15**) encoding the Cas9 enzyme into BL21 (DE3) (see **Note 16**). From these cells, new electro-competent cells are prepared which are shortly treated with Arabinose to induce expression of the λ -Red recombinase system co-encoded by pEcCas. Thus, the cells are ready to repair any double strand break of the chromosome aided by the λ -Red recombinase proteins. Upon providing the pEcgRNA N20_{*recA*} vector and the editing fragment, the sg-RNA_{*recA*}/Cas9 complex introduces a double strand break in the *recA* locus which is repaired with the editing fragment containing the *ho1* sequence. Since the sequence which is targeted by the sg-RNA_{*recA*} is deleted in this process, clones with successful genomic integration survive whereas other clones should die due to continuous chromosomal damage exerted by the sg-RNA_{*recA*}/Cas9 complex. A detailed graphical depiction of the workflow is shown in the original paper (**14**).

1. Prepare electro-competent *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) cells (see **Note 17**) by growing them in 35 mL LB media at 37°C and 200 rpm to an OD600 of 0.5 to 0.6. Cool the culture in ice water for 10 minutes, transfer to a 50 mL sterile tube and centrifuge (10 minutes, 4000 g, 4°C). After this point, all solutions in contact with the cells should be sterile and ice cold. Resuspend the pellet in 1 mL ddH₂O until homogeneous and fill up to 35 mL ddH₂O followed by centrifugation (10 minutes, 4000 g, 4°C). Re-suspend the pellet in 1 mL ddH₂O and transfer to a sterile 1.5 mL reaction tube. Centrifuge (10000 g, 30 s, 4°C) the solution and discard the supernatant and repeat re-suspension and centrifugation in the 1.5 mL reaction tube. Finally, re-suspend in 200 μ L ddH₂O for immediate usage or with 10% Glycerol (w/v) in ddH₂O for flash freezing in liquid nitrogen and storage.

2. Transfer 40 μL of electro-competent *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) to precooled 0.2cm electroporation cuvettes, add 100ng of pEcCas plasmid and conduct the electroporation at 1.8 kV followed by outgrowth for 30 minutes at 37 °C in 150 μL SOC media. Plate on LBK plates.
3. Grow a clone in 50 mL LBK media at 37 °C and 200 rpm until an OD_{600} of 0.35 is achieved, followed by addition of L-arabinose to a final concentration of 50mM. Incubate at 37 °C and 200 rpm for 30 minutes to induce expression of the λ -Red proteins. From this culture, again electro-competent cells should be prepared as outlined in step 1 to generate the “recombineering cells” (see **Note 18**).
4. Transform the electro-competent recombineering cells with 100 ng of the vector pEcgRNA N20_{recA} and 500 ng linear editing fragment stock (3.2.1.; step 5) according to the protocol in step 2, followed by plating on LBKSt plates (see **Note 19**).

3.2.3 Validation of successful genomic integration and curing of pEcCas/pEcgRNA from *E. coli* BL21 (DE3)

To check the successful integration of *ho1* into the *recA* locus, subject clones to UV irradiation since ΔrecA strains show markedly decreased survival rates under UV light. Positive clones still harbor both vectors pEcCas and pEcgRNA N20_{recA} which can be removed in the last part of the protocol. pEcCas encodes a second sg-RNA under the control of a rhamnose promoter which upon induction leads to the targeted degradation of pEcgRNA by Cas9. The removal of the pEcgRNA plasmid can be confirmed by simultaneous patching on LBK and LBKSt plates where successful degradation of the vector is indicated by survival on the first and death on the second plate. Optionally, the curing of pEcgRNA can also be confirmed by colony PCR. The vector pEcCas also contains the gene sequence of *sacB* coding for the enzyme levansucrase. This enzyme produces the toxic compound levan which turns the BL21 (DE3) pEcCas strain highly sensitive to sucrose. Thus, plating on sucrose containing plates efficiently removes pEcCas by applying this negative selection pressure. Lastly, the genomic integration is

confirmed by colony PCR using two primer pairs where in each one primer is binding in the genome and the other within *ho1*.

1. Re-suspend single colonies from the step above in 50 μ L of sterile ddH₂O to create a cell stock used here in step 1 and step 2 for each colony individually. Dip a sterile inoculation loop into the cell stock and streak a continuous line covering the full diameter of an LB plate, 6-8 samples can be fit on the same plate in parallel lines. Create a cell suspension of BL21 (DE3) as negative control and a Δ *recA* cloning strain like XL10-Gold as positive control. Cover half of the plate for later UV irradiation. To do that, cut the lid of a standard LB plate in half and cover first with a layer of aluminum foil followed by a layer of duct tape. Pre-warm the UV source in the UV crosslinker for 2 minutes, then set to energy mode and 5000 mJ. Turn the LB plate with the lines of bacterial samples facing the UV source and cover the plate so for each sample streaked as a line, half of it is covered. Irradiate with UV light (workflow Figure 2B; see **Note 20**) and place the LB plate at 37 °C overnight.
2. In parallel to the UV sensitivity tests, use 5 μ L each of the same cell stocks as above to inoculate 4 mL of LBK media + 10 mM rhamnose and grow at 200 rpm for 6h at 37 °C. This is inducing the sg-RNA which targets pEcgRNA leading to degradation of the plasmid. Spin the cultures down at 4000 g (5 min, RT) and re-suspend in 4 mL LB media and grow at 200 rpm for 2 h at 37 °C.
3. With a marker, divide an LBSu plate in four equal parts. Use a sterile inoculation loop to streak 4 different LB cultures per LBSu plate to induce removal of the pEcCas plasmid. Thin out the liquid cultures appropriately as the next step requires single colonies.
4. On the next day, check the UV treated plates from step 1. Samples which did grow in the shielded environment but not in the UV exposed areas are *recA* negative and likely positive for the genomic integration. Check the LBSu plates from 2; single colonies from this plate, which are UV sensitive and thus *recA negative*, are further processed. Subdivide 3 plates (LB, LBK, LBSt) into around 30 small rectangular squares with a printed template which is laid under each

plate (see also **(14)**). Touch single colonies on the LBSu plate with a sterile inoculation loop and patch 0.5 cm lines on each of the 3 plates for each single colony (see **Note 21**). Incubate the 3 plates at 37°C overnight. Clones which grow on the LB but not LBK or LBSt plate were successfully cured from the pEcCas and pEcgRNA vectors meaning their complete removal.

5. Streak a clone which is sensitive to kanamycin and streptomycin on an LB plate using an inoculation loop to retrieve single colonies. Dip single colonies with a pipette tip in 10 µL of sterile ddH₂O at room temperature to create a cell stock. Confirm the correct sequence of the *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 *ho1* in the genome of BL21 (DE3) by PCR using 1 µL of cell stock per clone. Utilize a premixed formulation containing a DNA Polymerase with proof-reading capabilities and 2 primer pairs (seq_genomic_fwd/rev; seq_genomic_pncC_fwd/rev) to confirm the successful genomic integration by standard PCR (see **Note 22**). Purify the PCR products of these reactions with a DNA cleanup kit. To the liquid PCR mix, add three times the volume of the column binding buffer followed by the standard DNA cleanup procedure. Send the purified PCR products for Sanger sequencing using sufficient primers to confirm the correct integration of *ho1* into the *recA* locus of BL21 (DE3).
6. From the cell stock of step 5, inoculate 10 mL LB media and grow till an OD₆₀₀ of 1. Mix 500 µL of cell suspension with 500 µL of 50 % glycerol and store these stocks at -80 °C.
7. Optional: quick protocol to test successful *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 *ho1* genomic integration in BL21 (DE3). Inoculate BL21 (DE3) WT and BL21 (DE3) HO1 in 10 mL LB media without any additives and grow till reaching the stationary phase (>20 h). Spin down 1 mL of culture each (10000 g, RT, 30 s) and check the color of the supernatant, the BL21 (DE3) HO1 sample should show green coloring. Measure the supernatants on the Nanodrop, a distinct peak around 400 nm should be visible if biliverdin is successfully produced by the genomic integration strain (see **Note 23**).

Fig. 2. Principle of CRISPR/Cas9 genomic integration and UV sensitivity tests. A) Overview of events after transforming the pEcgRNA N20_{recA} plasmid into recombineering cells which contain pEcCas encoding the Cas9 enzyme. The Cas9 protein (orange) is guided to its target locus by the sg-RNA_{recA} where it is causing double strand cleavage, here in the *recA* locus. Aided by the λ -Red proteins, the editing fragment containing the *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 *ho1* sequence is inserted into the *recA* locus, guided by the upper homology (“up hom”) and downstream homology sequences (“down hom”). Thus, the *ho1* sequence replaces the *recA* sequence which is targeted by the Cas9 nuclease. The result is an *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) expression strain where *ho1* is under the control of an IPTG inducible T7 promoter. B) Workflow of the UV sensitivity test. This test can be conducted after the transformation of pEcCas recombineering cells with pEcgRNA N20_{recA} which results in the introduction

of the *ho1* gene as described in panel A. The deletion/truncation of *recA* leads to a bacterial strain which is more sensitive to UV irradiation than *E. coli* BL21 (DE3). This opens the possibility for an easy screening system for genomic integration of *ho1* into the *recA* locus. As described in 3.2.3 step 1, use an inoculation loop to streak clones with the potential *ho1* insertion on a LB plate. Cover half of the plate with an UV light blocking material and irradiate the plate with UV light, the streaked cells should face the UV source. Clones which show survival under the UV protection but die upon UV exposure are *recA* negative and are highly likely to show correct integration of *ho1* into the chromosome.

3.3 A general phytochrome expression protocol

1. Choose your desired expression system (for example from table 3) and transform the expression strain with a vector containing the phytochrome and/or a heme oxygenase. In our case, the overexpression vector is a pETM11 vector with a Kanamycin resistance cassette. Plate on LBK plates (LBCK in version 1) and incubate overnight at 37°C.
2. Scratch off multiple colonies (20-50, see **Note 24**) of the plates and inoculate them in 100 mL (see **Note 25**) of LB media containing appropriate antibiotics, 0.3 % glucose (w/v) and 8.5 mM MgCl₂ in a 1 L baffled flask (see **Notes 26**). Shake at 130 rpm at 37 °C until an OD₆₀₀ of 0.8-1 is achieved.
3. Transfer 20-30 mL of pre-culture into 1 L of LB media containing appropriate antibiotics, 0.3 % glucose (w/v) and 8.5 mM MgCl₂ in a 2.5 L baffled flask. Shake at 130 rpm at 37 °C until an OD₆₀₀ of 0.5 is achieved.
4. Add δ -Ala to a final concentration of 10 μ g/mL and put the flasks into a shaker precooled to 18 °C. Shake at 18°C, 130 rpm for 30 minutes to cool down the culture (see **Note 27**).
5. Add IPTG to a final concentration of 0.25 mM and shake overnight at 18 °C, 130 rpm. Harvest the bacteria by centrifugation at 4500 rpm. Strong green coloration of the pellet is usually already a good indication of successful phytochrome production, alternatively conduct sodium

dodecylsulfate polyacrylamide gelelectrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) with samples before and after induction and check for overexpression bands on the gel. Store the pellet at -20 °C in the freezer for further processing (for comments on advantages of different expression approaches see **Note 4 and 5**).

4 Notes

1. Under the link <https://doi.org/10.3217/tv97k-t9f33>, nucleotide sequences of expression vectors and the modified pEcgRNA vector are deposited. The file Data_comment.pdf contains an overview of the files deposited whereas the folder “Data” contains the deposited nucleotide sequences.
2. When using the webpage ATUM, set the parameters to *E. coli* K12 MG1655, PAM NGG, wild-type Cas9. Insert the sequence around the desired cutting site (approx. 200 bp) and choose the N20 nucleotide spacer with the highest scores. Alternatively, choose other webpages to generate N20 sequences or consult the table in the supplements of this paper (**18**), which contains a list of N20 sequences which work in *E. coli*. Carefully read this paper as some of these sequences only work efficiently with simultaneous knock down of the *recA* gene locus. To design the N20 nucleotide spacer, the upstream and downstream homology sequences, as well as the seq_genomic primers, use the *recA* nucleotide sequence accessible on www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov for the reference chromosome of *E. coli* strain K-12 substr. MG1655 (Sequence ID NC_000913.3, region 2822708 to 2823769, this sequence is on the negative strand). When designing the N20 sequence and the editing fragment, keep in mind that after recombineering the target site of the sg-RNA should be deleted with the insert of choice to avoid continuous chromosome cutting and cell death.
3. When working with the pEcgRNA plasmid as deposited at Addgene, remember that it contains the *ccdB* gene, which allows only the usage of cloning strains to which the gene product is not toxic, like XL10-Gold. However, when transforming a mutated vector where the N20 nucleotide spacer sequence successfully replaced the *ccdB* sequence, this circumstance can be handy. Use a strain which cannot tolerate *ccdB* like NEBalpha so only clones where the plasmid was successfully mutated to contain the N20 nucleotide spacer can grow.

4. At least for chemically competent *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) cells, co-transformation of the pT7 HO1 helper plasmid with the pET vector containing the POI is very inefficient. Instead, BL21 (DE3) should be transformed with pT7 HO1, clones selected and again made chemically competent before transformation with a vector containing the POI. Note that at least in our hands, this BL21(DE3) pT7 HO1 cells have a limited shelf life at -20 °C and should be newly prepared at least every 4-6 months. Sometimes even clone to clone variation of the BL21 (DE3) pT7 HO1 cells can occur, therefore it pays off to pick at least 4 clones separately for preparation of competent cells and testing their expression capabilities. When producing a new stock for the helper plasmid pT7 HO1 Cm^R, be aware to not use a cloning strain with a natural antibiotic resistance against chloramphenicol like XL10-Gold.
5. Expression yields in the different systems can depend on the phytochrome of interest but a trend is observed depending on the system used for biliverdin generation. The following list is sorted from higher to lower expression yields: a) Expression strain with genomic integration of *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 *ho1* (version 4); b) pT7 HO1 (*Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803) helper plasmid-based expression; c) Bi-cistronic expression plasmid using the HO/phytochrome architecture separated by a nucleotide spacer (version 3); d) Bi-cistronic expression plasmid using the HO/phytochrome architecture with overlapping stop and start codon (version 2). It should be noted, that the difference between the genomic integration strain and the pT7 helper plasmid approach are minute and might be within errors observed in batch-to-batch reproducibility. Expression yield-wise, both of these approaches outperform the bi-cistronic expression systems. It should be noted, that between the two different bi-cistronic architectures – separation by a nucleotide spacer versus overlapping ORFs – deviations in expression yields are minute. Still, co-translational expression of overlapping coding regions is the closest to the natural situation at least observed for some BphPs. Though the yield potentially drops, this system has advantages because of its straight forward usage and its usability in circumstances where yield is less important like high-throughput approaches. Apart

from slightly higher yields, genomic integration provides benefits like increased shelf life and slightly faster growth characteristics compared to the pT7 helper plasmid-based expression.

6. The majority of the *M*sHO coding sequence was codon optimized for expression in *E. coli*, however the last 21 nucleotides remained in its natural sequence context to preserve potentially important sequence properties for bi-cistronic expression. The decision to protect specifically 21 nucleotides of the HO gene was based on the idea to at least include a potential cryptic Shine-Dalgarno sequence in the upstream CDS, but the influence of not codon optimizing this region was not tested in detail. For a general review on overlapping genes see **(13)**.
7. The overlapping sequences in the *M*sHO/*M*sPadC expression plasmid constitute the upstream *ho* CDS stop codon and the downstream start codon corresponding to the His₆-tag. In comparison, the *I*sHO/*I*sPadC expression plasmid harbors *I*sHO, the nucleotide spacer and then the start codon of the His₆-tag. Although the inclusion of the His-tags for the PadC proteins deviates from the genetic context found in the organisms, this setup still leads to sufficiently high expression levels. As mentioned, *M*sHO has an overlapping stop codon with its phytochrome whereas in *I*sHO there is a nucleotide spacer before the adjacent phytochrome. However, at least for over-expressions, *M*sHO can be cloned with an overlapping start codon in front of *I*sPadC and *I*sHO can be cloned with a nucleotide spacer in front of *M*sPadC and in both cases, the phytochrome is still produced loaded with BV. In our tests, the highest phytochrome yield was achieved for *I*sHO cloned with a nucleotide spacer in front of *M*sPadC. However, cloning of *I*sHO with an overlap of the stop codon or *M*sHO with a nucleotide spacer was not tested.
8. The overlap extension protocol used for the insertion of the *M*sHO/*I*sHO into the pETM11 vector was first described in **(19)**. It should be noted that the molar excess range (around 250x) of the megaprimer (aka insert), the annealing temperature of 55°C and using 20 cycles are pivotal for the success of the method.

9. First and foremost, it is strictly necessary to read and understand the two publications where the pEcCas/pEcgRNA **(14)** and an earlier version **(20)** are presented. The genomic integration location for heterologous protein expression matters, thus, the *recA* locus was chosen as stable integration at this chromosomal location showed decent expression levels for *E. coli* in the literature **(21)**. Furthermore, *recA* knockout/knockdown was also shown to aid the efficiency of CRISPR/Cas9 mediated recombineering in *E. coli* **(18)**. For a general overview about CRISPR/Cas9 basics and methods see <https://www.addgene.org/guides/crispr/>.
10. The overlapping primer design for the insertion of the N20 nucleotide spacer into the pEcgRNA vector was performed according to the protocols described by Liu and Naismith et al., 2008 **(22)**.
11. If you want to design an additional/alternative N20 nucleotide spacer sequence to target a different gene locus, experimentally try multiple (at least 3) designs to decide on the most suitable one. Run pre-experiments on their DNA double strand cutting efficiency. Create electro-competent cells of your choice harboring the induced pEcCas vector as described in 3.2.2., steps 1 and 3. Transform these recombineering ready cells with pEcgRNA empty (no sg-RNA) and in parallel pEcgRNA plus the novel sg-RNA sequence. Count the colonies on both plates, the pEcgRNA empty plate should show a multitude of colonies whereas the second plate should show very few if any colonies. The ratio between these plates (# colonies pEcgRNA N20/# colonies pEcgRNA empty) should usually be <5% to indicate a high efficiency of double strand breakage by Cas9 in the desired locus.
12. Instead of amplifying the homology sequences from the chromosome and assembling the editing fragment by Gibson assembly, the editing fragment can also be ordered from a nucleotide synthesis company. If you do that and want to target a gene locus which might show variability between strains, one could think about amplifying the gene region of interest with PCR and sequencing it to confirm that the regions targeted show the expected sequence. Also remember to not codon optimize the sequence of the homology regions.

13. We initially inserted the editing fragment into the pEcgRNA+N20_{recA} vector mainly because we thought it would be easier to handle that way. When generating the BL21 (DE3) pEcCas arabinose induced recombineering cells, transformation of the whole pEcgRNA N20_{recA} +editing fragment works for genomic insertion. However, we realized that co-transformation of the pEcgRNA+ N20_{recA} vector with a highly concentrated linear editing fragment stock (generated in 3.2.1., step 5) works more efficiently in our hands. Sidenote: Due to the study context in which the pEcCas/pEcgRNA system was intended to be used, the resistance cassette of the pEcgRNA vector was exchanged to Amp^R. If your study design does not require this, it is strongly suggested to not follow this complication. Therefore, the backbone amplification primers are not provided in the manuscript as they include the generation of overhangs to an ampicillin resistance cassette.
14. Note that in the shown example, not the full *recA* sequence is deleted but the start codon and roughly 300 bp of the CDS are kept which resembles a truncation of the protein. To avoid translation of *ho1* under the *recA* promoter, the *ho1* ORF was inserted on the opposite strand compared to the reading direction of *recA*.
15. For isolating the pEcCas plasmid, it is recommended to use midiprep scale isolation kits since the vector copy number is very low.
16. To generate *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) pEcCas cells, high quality chemically competent cells can be used, however, their transformation efficiency is extremely low and retrieval of positive transformants is not guaranteed.
17. When using electrocompetent cells, it is pivotal to use plasmid preparations which were eluted with highly pure ddH₂O to prevent arcing.
18. When preparing the electro-competent BL21 (DE3) pEcCas arabinose induced cells, it is highly recommended to immediately pursue with the workflow. Shelf life of flash frozen cell stocks in 10 % glycerol at -80 °C was observed to be less than 2 weeks.

19. After the last recombineering step (3.2.2, step 4), successful genomic integration can already be confirmed using the colony PCR/sequencing approach. However, this step is rather time consuming and, since not a single clone was observed which was UV sensitive and did not have the correct insertion, might not be needed.
20. The exact dose for UV irradiation needs to be empirically determined as it strongly depends on the *E. coli* strain used. Conduct experiments to identify the ideal dosage which kills a $\Delta recA$ cloning strain but not your *recA* positive expression strain.
21. In our hands, the least efficient step in the pEcCas/pEcgRNA workflow is the rhamnose induced removal of the pEcgRNA plasmid. Thus, the patching experiment (3.2.3, 2) should be conducted with at least 30 clones to retrieve a strain which is cured from pEcCas and pEcgRNA. Since the biliverdin producing properties of the strain were more important to us than removal of pEcgRNA, the final generated strain used for successful expression of phytochromes still contains this plasmid and is therefore ampicillin resistant. It was thus termed BL21 (DE3) *recA::ho1* pEcgRNA. Removal of pEcCas works very efficiently with high curing success.
22. To confirm correct insertion of the gene of interest, it is recommended to use at least 2 primer pairs for amplification and sending the PCR product purified with a DNA cleanup kit for Sanger sequencing to check the sequence of the insert and the upstream/downstream regions. In this case primer pair 1 (seq_genomic_fwd/rev) binds upstream of the *recA* sequence which is not part of the editing fragment and within the *Synechocystis* sp. PCC6803 *ho1* sequence, respectively. Primer pair 2 (seq_genomic_pncC_fwd/rev) binds within the *ho1* gene and a neighboring gene to *recA*, here *pncC*.
23. For the optional quick protocol to confirm active *ho1* in BL21 (DE3) (3.2.3, step 7), it is not necessary to add additives like δ -ALA or IPTG as the leaky expression from the T7 promoter and the natural heme metabolism in the strain is sufficient to allow biliverdin accumulation. In fact, it was observed that addition of δ -ALA or IPTG in the absence of a phytochrome which would sequester biliverdin, leads to less obvious green coloring of the culture supernatant.

24. Inoculation with multiple instead of a single transformant can improve the reproducibility of the expression process. Furthermore, this allows to conduct the expression protocol from inoculating the pre-culture to adding IPTG in 1 day which in our experience also improves reproducibility.
25. The size of the pre-cultures scale in relation to how many liters of media should be inoculated. For example, if 12 flasks with 1 L media each should be inoculated, generate at least 400 mL of pre-culture ideally in one flask to aid uniformity over all flasks.
26. Proper aeration is key, use baffled flasks and the culture volume should be maximally 20% of the flask volume in all liquid culturing steps. In addition, cultures should be shaken thoroughly, we typically use 130 rpm on a 25 mm orbit shaker.
27. At least for our proteins, the cooling of the culture to 18°C prior to IPTG addition (3.3; 4) is absolutely essential for proper expression of soluble holophytochrome to the point where neglecting this step leads to complete failure of soluble protein production.

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